

Antibacterial Properties of Ginger (*Zingiber Officinale L.*) Towards Increasing the Shelf Life of Fresh Catfish (*Clarias Gariepinus*)

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Abstract: Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) is very important for the abundance of animal protein it contains. However, there is so much loss of this precious protein due to wanton spoilage occasioned by the activities of microbes chief among which is bacteria. The aim of this study was increasing the shelf life of catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) on application of a paste of ginger. The fish samples were each treated with 0g; 10g; 20g and 30g of ginger per kilogram (Kg-1) of the fish. The results revealed that there was a significant difference in the cfu ($P=0.002 < 0.05$). It was observed that there was an inverse relationship between the cfu and the concentrations of ginger. As the concentration of ginger increased, the cfu decreased hence, the 30g of ginger had the lowest cfu of 1.98×10^6 . The control had an average colony forming unit (cfu) of 4.53×10^6 . The results also showed that, of the bacterial flora isolated, the gram negative bacteria such as *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* were the most prevalent. Furthermore, the results revealed that, the treated ginger samples had a more tolerable spoilage pattern after fours than the control as affirmed by panel ratings. The progression showed that the highest concentration had a four-hour lapse before deterioration. The results from this research concludes that ginger is efficacious in increasing the shelf life of catfish by a further four hours when treated with 30g of ginger per kilogram of the fish. It is therefore recommended that a greater dose (60g-100g) of ginger per kilogram of fish be employed in increasing the shelf-life of fresh catfish from 4 hours to days.

Keywords: Antibacterial, Catfish, Ginger, Microbes, Shelf-life

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Introduction

Catfish also known as African sharp tooth catfish belongs to the family Claridae. It is a large fish [1] which is notable for its animal protein. The production of catfish in Nigeria has witnessed a momentous growth in the last 20 years. This becomes evident owing to the attendant problems associated with beef which hitherto was the main source of animal protein [2]. Despite this importance attached to fish, it faces the bane of spoilage due to bacterial activities.

Bacteria agents are the most culpable in causing disease to aquatic organisms. Apart from interfering with the quality of water, they also cause post-harvest spoilage therefore reducing the quality of the fish hence great loss.

Spices are edible plant materials added to food to cause delay in rancidity or antioxidative as well as bacteriostatic properties. Spices and herbs are rich sources of antioxidants [3]. They have been used in food and beverages to enhance flavor, aroma and colour. [4] revealed that citrus (*Citrus aurantium*) peel extract has good antioxidant and antimicrobial activities on the shelf life of Indian mackerel increasing it by 2 days compared to control by delaying the spoilage mechanisms when stored at -2°C . Similarly, a combination of citrus and pomegranate peel extract and chitosan nanoparticles have proven to increase the shelf life of silver carp fillets [5]. Ginger is a flowering plant whose rhizome is used as a spice [6]. It is consumed in many parts of the world for its several purposes such as, seasoning in Indian recipes, herb tea, as well as flavouring in Asian cuisines such as seafood, meat and vegetarian dishes [7] (Akram *et al.*, 2011). The ginger root is used in Nigeria as herbal medicine and in homes as spice for pap, as soup flavouring and in other delicacies, drinks and treatment for various illness.

The lack of adequate storage facilities in Nigeria results in nutritional loss in catfish. Aside this, there is a large economic loss due to the activities of microorganisms. The easiest storage facility of fresh fish is the refrigerator but the unstable power supply makes this ineffective. In addition, synthetic additives are widely used in fish processing industries to control the process of lipid oxidation as well as microbial growth, the present trend is to decrease their use because of the growing concern about the safety of such chemical additives. As such, there has to be an alternative means of preservation to avoid total loss, hence this research.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted in the Laboratory of the Department of Biological Sciences, Nigerian Police Academy, Wudil and the Food Technology Laboratory, Kano States University of Science and Technology, Wudil Kano State.

Procurement and Preparation of Samples

Twenty-eight (28) pieces of catfish with an average weight of 1Kg were purchased from retailers (dealers) in Wudil Market. The fish were packed in clean polythene bags and transported on motorcycle to the laboratory at the Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil. Each fish was disembowelled and prepared into butterfly cuts according to the method of [8]. The sides were washed with saline water and they were put into four groups of seven fish each. Enough fresh ginger was obtained from Wudil market. The outer coat was removed, they were washed very well and ground properly into very smooth paste and applied as spice onto the four groups of seven fish at the concentrations of 0g (control) ; 10g, 20g and 30g ginger per Kg of fish respectively. The fish were packaged in clean foil papers and examined after four hours. They were then subjected to organoleptic, macroscopic, microscopic and biochemical analyses.

Preparation of Nutrient Agar

Nutrient agar was prepared using the manufacturer's guide (Standard procedures).

Preparation of Bacteria Culture

Bacterial samples were collected by swabbing through the skin and intestine of the fish and blending with 10ml of sterile 0.1% peptone water. Appropriate sample dilutions were made (10^{-1} - 10^{-5}) with sterile peptone water. Aliquots of 1ml of serial dilution were inoculated on petri dishes using pour plate technique.

Identification of Bacteria

Pure cultures of bacteria were prepared using the streak method. Cultures were characterized and identified using various morphological characteristics, such as macroscopic and microscopic and biochemical tests such as catalase, oxidases urease Vogues-Proskauer, motility and respiratory tests.

Macroscopic Analysis

The bacteria colonies on the petri dishes were examined using magnifying lens. Features such as elevation, texture, margin, pigmentation and shape were observed.

Microscopic Analysis

This was done using the oil immersion objective lens (x100) to check Gram's stain, morphology and spore formation. Gram's stain method was used as an initial procedure in the identification of the unknown bacteria species.

Biochemical Analysis

The tests carried out included catalase, oxidase, urease, Vogues-Proskauer (VP) and motility tests according to the methods of [9]Reiner, (2016).

Catalase Test

The test was carried out by using the method of [9] by using a wooden Applicator to put a small amount of a bacteria colony in a test tube containing five drops of 3% hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). The test tube was then placed against a dark background and observed for immediate bubble formation at the end of the wooden Applicator stick. Formation of bubbles indicates catalase positive.

Oxidase Test

The bacteria colony was smeared using a wooden loop on a commercially prepared paper disc (that has been moistened with sterile distilled water). This was observed for the development of the deep blue or purple colour within 30 seconds which indicates oxidase positive bacteria.

Urease Test

The test was carried out by inoculating urea broth with test organism and then incubating for 48hrs. The media used for urea test contained a pH indicator, phenol red which turns to pink at alkaline pH. The red colour observed indicates the presence of urease positive bacteria.

Voges-Proskauer Test (VP)

This test was done by inoculating a tube of VP broth with a pure culture of the test organism. This was incubated for 24hours at $35^\circ C$ after which an aliquot of 1ml of broth was put in a clean test tube, then 0.6 ml of 5% alpha naphthol was added. This was followed by the addition of 0.2ml of 40% KOH. The tube was shaken gently and was then exposed to atmospheric oxygen and allowed to stand for 10 minutes development of a brownish to pink colour indicates a positive VP test.

Motility Test

The motility of different bacterial cells was observed using the "Hanging drop" method. This was done by preparing a semi-solid agar medium in a test tube and then inoculating with a straight wire, making a single stab down the centre of the tube half the depth of the medium. The test tubes were incubated at $37^\circ c$ and examined at an interval of 6hrs. [10] Non-motile bacteria give growth that are confined to the stab-line, have defined margins and leave the surrounding medium clearly transparent while motile bacteria would typically give diffuse and lazy growths that spread throughout the medium rendering it slightly opaque.

Colony Count

The total colony count of catfish was calculated using the automated colony counter on the fifth serial dilution.

Organoleptic Analysis

Subjective evaluation of the product quality was carried out in accordance with the method of [10] Poste et al. (1991) by a panel of twenty five (25) coded samples of 1-4 where;

1 = control

2-4 = treatments

This was accompanied with questionnaires which were presented to panelists. The quality attributes studied included taste, odour and texture. The scale used was from 1-5 where

1 = very poor

2 = poor

3 = Normal

4 = Good

5 = very good

Results

Morphological Analysis of Bacteria

Macroscopic examination

The macroscopic examination showed that 50 % of the bacteria examined had a round shape (Staphylococcus, Klebsiella and Serratia spp. while 16.67 % each were observed to be oval, rod or sphere (Table 1). The results also indicated that, texturally, E. coli, Klebsiella, Pseudomonas and Serratia species were observed to be mucoid. Similarly, three of the above four were unbonate in terms of elevation. Furthermore, 50 % of the bacteria had entire margins. However, all the bacteria studied had different pigmentation. For instance, E. coli was grey while Staphylococcus was golden yellow and Pseudomonas was diffusible green (Table 1).

Table 1: Macroscopic characteristics of the different bacteria colonies observed

Bacteria	Shape	Pigment	Texture	Elevation	Margin
Escherichia coli	Rod	Grey	Mucoid	Slightly convex	Entire
Staphylococcus sp	Round	Golden Yellow	Smooth	Convex	Entire
Streptococcus sp	Sphere	Light brown	Moist	Umblicate	Raised
Klebsiella sp	Round	Pale yellow	Mucoid	Umbonate	Undulate
Pseudomonas sp	Oval	Diffusible green	Mucoid	Umbonate	Wavy
Serratia sp	Round	Red	Mucoid	Umbonate	Entire

Microscopic examination

The results of the microscopic examination revealed that 66.67% of the total bacteria were Gram negative while Staphylococcus Streptococcus representing 33.33 % of the total bacteria were Gram positive. It was further revealed that different shapes including straight rods, cocci and diplococci were observed among the bacteria. Furthermore, the bacteria exhibited different ranges of size. For instance Serratia had the highest size range of 5-30 while the least size was observed in Pseudomonas (0.5- 1.0)(Table 2).

Table 2: Microscopic characteristics of the different bacteria colonies observed

Bacteria	Gram's Stain	Morphology	Size μ	Spores	Apearance
Escherichia coli	-	Straight rod	1.1-1.5	-	Singly or pair
Staphylococcus sp	+	Cocci	0.5-1.5	-	Grape-like cluster
Streptococcus sp	+	Diplococci	0.6-1.0	-	Pair
Klebsiella sp	-	Straight rod	0.1-1.5	+	Pairs, chains or end to end
Pseudomonas sp	-	Rod	0.5-1.0	-	Small rod
Serratia sp	-	Rod	5.0-30.0	-	Short rod

Keys + = Positive; - = Negative

Biochemical Reaction

Colony Count

The bactericidal effect of ginger was observed on catfish as the results revealed that there was a steady decline in the number of colonies formed as treatment increased. For instance *Escherichia coli* formed the most dominant colonies while *Serratia sp.* colony appeared just once in the control. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) test showed that there is significant difference in the colony units formed by different bacterial cells showing that ginger has bacterio-static properties. From the result, $P = 0.002 < 0.05$. (Table 3)

Table 3: Colony forming units of the different bacteria

Bacteria	Sample			
	One	Two	Three	Four
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	0.72×10^7	0.64×10^7	0.42×10^7	0.37×10^7
<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	0.61×10^7	0.57×10^7	0.25×10^7	0.19×10^7
<i>Streptococcus sp.</i>	0.43×10^7	0.35×10^7	0.21×10^7	0.17×10^7
<i>Klebsiella sp.</i>	0.39×10^7	0.31×10^7	0.27×10^7	0.21×10^7
<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	0.56×10^7	0.49×10^7	0.32×10^7	0.25×10^7
<i>Serratia sp.</i>	0.01×10^7			

Biochemical Reactions

The biochemical tests revealed that all the bacteria tested negative for oxidase with the exception of *Pseudomonas sp.* elsewhere, only *Streptococcus sp.* and *Klebsella sp.* tested negative for the catalase test. All the bacteria examined were facultative anaerobic except *Pseudomonas sp.* which is an aerobe, although some can be obligate anaerobe and aerobe respectively.

Table 4: Biochemical Reactions of the different bacteria observed

Bacteria	Catalase	Oxidase	Urease	V-P	Motility	Respiration
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	-	-	-	Motile	Facultative anaerobe
<i>Staphylococcus sp</i>	+	-	+	+	Non motile	Facultative anaerobe
<i>Streptococcus sp</i>	-	-	-	-	Non motile	Anaerobe
<i>Klebsiella sp</i>	-	-	+	+	Non motile	Aerobe/Anaerobe
<i>Pseudomonas sp</i>	+	+	-	-	Motile	Aerobe
<i>Serratia sp</i>	+	-	+	+	Motile	Facultative anaerobe

Key: V-P= Vogues-Proskauer

Organoleptic Analysis

Taste

Results of the Panel ratings revealed that 80% of the panelist gave the control a very poor score while the remaining 20% gave it a poor score. The results also shows that only the sample 3 (20g) and sample 4 (30g) got a good rating from 12% and 48% of the panelists respectively. Elsewhere, majority of the panelists (48%) felt the sample 3 (20g) had a normal taste (Fig 1).

Fig 1: Rating for Taste Attributes

Odour

The results of the treatment of catfish with ginger indicated that an average number (48 %) of the panelists found the odour of the fish post-treatment tolerable. The results also showed that 76 % of the panelists rated the untreated fish very poorly (Fig 2). However, 32 % of them felt the odour from treatment 2 was poor. Similarly, 40% of the panelists felt the sample three had a good odour while 12% felt it had a poor odour (Fig 2). The panel rating of odour attribute of the different samples is represented in fig 4.3

Fig 2: Rating for odour character

Texture

The results further revealed that there was a progressive pattern with regards to the attribute of texture as was observed by the panelists' ratings. For instance, 60% rated the control as very poor while just 4% gave sample 4 (30g) a poor rating, none of the panelists felt the control deserved a normal rating although, 40%, 48% and 24% of the panelists felt sample 2, sample 3 and sample 4 respectively were normal. The best rating was given to sample 4 with 32% of the panelists giving it a very good rating, only sample three came close with 12% panel score rating it as very good (Fig 3).

Fig 3: Rating for Texture character

Discussion

The results revealed a highly significant difference in the colony forming units of different bacterial cells suggesting that ginger has bacterio-static properties. This result agrees with the earlier work of [11]. The results indicated that there was an inverse relationship between the cfu and the concentration of the ginger paste. As the concentration of the paste was increased from 10g to 30g, there was a corresponding decrease in the number of the colony forming units suggesting that the higher level of the ginger paste had more effect in bringing down the bacterial load on the fish. This was observed across all the microflora.

The bacteria isolated were dominated by gram negative bacteria especially *Escherichia coli*. The bacteria flora of the serial solution was a reflection of the bacteria composition of the skin, gills and stomach of the *Clarias gariepinus*. This type of scenario was also observed earlier as reported by [12]. In addition, the microflora of caught fish and other aquatic specimens is largely a reflection of the microbial quality of the water where they were harvested. This might explain why a single colony of *Serratia marcescens* was observed in the control. The microflora of the catfish studied are *Escherichia coli*, *Streptococcus sp.*, *Pseudomonas sp.*, *Staphylococcus sp.*, *Klebsellia sp.*, *Serratia sp.* [13] reported similar bacterial species in their study of the bacterial flora of *Clarias gariepinus* and *Oreochromis niloticus* from Ibadan, South west Nigeria. It is also important to note that, the commensal bacterial flora included facultative pathogens. This group of bacteria could give rise to fish disease when subjected to stress. They can also be potential pathogens to humans and implicated to be fish borne. *Serratia sp.* cause bacteriuria while *Pseudomonas sp.* had been isolated in wounds, burns, eyes and ear infections.

The use of natural additives have significantly improved the preservation of this fish. [14] reported that, significant reductions in the free fatty acid (FFA), peroxide value (PV) and thiobarbituric acid reactive substance (TBARS) values were observed in samples treated with turmeric and smoked for 1 h (T1) and 2 h (T2) compared to their respective control samples. This is made possible because of the phytochemical constituent gingerol [15] of the research plant extract which normally disrupts the physical attribute of the outer membrane of the bacteria.

Some pathogenic and potentially pathogenic microorganisms including *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus sp.* have been reported to survive when undercooked and precooked fish foods were stored at freezing temperatures. After death, incorrect or inadequate handling can introduce bacteria to the flesh resulting in spoilage. The natural flora of fish that play a predominant role in spoilage include the genera *Pseudomonas*, *Vibrio*, *Micrococcus*, *Achromonas*, *Corynebacterium* and *Flavobacterium* [16]. *Proteus* and *Pseudomonas sp.* are among the major spoilage bacteria at near freezing temperatures. *Pseudomonas sp.* was one of the bacteria isolated from this study. That probably is one of the reasons why there was quicker spoilage among the untreated fish samples. In order to prolong the shelf life of fish, it is essential to control these spoilage bacteria.

There were disparities in the bacterial load of the control and the other three treatments. The maximum bacterial count obtained in cfu was 10^7 . This result is comparable with that reported by [17] and [18] who reported counts in the range of 10^6 to 10^8 respectively, but lower than that earlier reported by [19]. They reported counts in the range of 10^{12} - 10^{13} cfu in their study of water samples from catfish ponds in Jos metropolis. [20] reported lower counts in the range of 10^4 - 10^5 on the skin of *Clarias sp.* The outcome of the present study falls within the standard range of 10^2 - 10^7 cfu as has also been alluded to by earlier researchers [21],[22]. The control had the highest microbial load as compared to all other treatments of the fish studied. This could be due to the presence of residue of its constant exposure and contact with the environment such as pond water, air, etc. [23] also made a similar observation.

Furthermore, the result of the organoleptic analyses of the catfish showed that the control samples received lower panel scores than the ginger paste-treated samples with regards to taste, texture and odour. It has been reported that lipid oxidation generally leads to deterioration [24]. This can be detected by organoleptic evaluation [25]. Also, microbial breakdown of amino acids has been reported to

lead to bitterness, bad odour and texture of the flesh of fish [26]. The taste panel rating showed that treated samples were rated better than untreated samples in all the parameters studied. However, [11] observed no significant difference among the treatments in all the organoleptic parameters measured. This may be due to the fact that, the catfish they used were smoked and stored for twenty-one days. Similarly, [27] in their research also observed little difference among the treatments which may be as a result of their use of garlic to examine chicken sausage examined for 21 days. Further test also revealed that the sample with the highest concentration lasted for 4 hours before signs of deterioration manifested especially, when compared with the untreated fish samples. This is an indication of the inhibiting activity of the ginger extract, which, has been reported to contain phytochemicals especially polyphenolics. [28] had reported that, the active hydroxyl groups present in the molecular structure of polyphenols are the active components that can interact with the free radicals to inhibit lipid oxidation. Polyphenols like flavonoids are also present in ginger. This can increase the shelf-life of an organism. Climatic conditions such as temperature and relative humidity could also have played an important role in this hence longer or shorter readings could be obtained in different localities. The treated fish was adjudged to be better with respect to the texture and odour. This may be as a result of the presence of antioxidants in ginger. It has been suggested that some pathogenic microorganisms mostly do not produce sensory deterioration, which act as a challenge for food safety. This has made the use of spices on fresh fish imperative [29].

Conclusion

This study has shown that ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) has some anti-oxidative and anti-bacterial effects which can retard oxidative rancidity, inhibit bacterial growth, impact acceptable flavor and thus, extend the shelf-life of fish like *Clarias gariepinus*. Furthermore, it has shown that the higher the level of ginger used, the higher the effectiveness of ginger. Although the microbial load observed did not exceed the recommended standards, several potential spoilage and pathogenic organisms were components of the bacterial flora, presence of which could constitute a public health risk and economic loss if the fish is not properly handled.

Conflict of Interest

It is difficult to assign Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) or no observable adverse effect level (NOEL) for the plant extracts [30]. The safety assessment of plant extracts is also complicated by many factors such as compositional diversity, lack of identity of the active ingredients etc[14]. Most plant derived extracts have been generally considered to be safe by USFDA (21 Code of Federal Regulations CFR 182, 184).

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